

THE EUROPEAN AND NATIONAL LEGISLATION THAT REGULATE THE OPTIONAL QUALITY TERM “MOUNTAIN PRODUCT”

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Abstract

The mountain products are an integral part of the mountain territories' image and are often associated by the consumers with the landscapes, customs and local traditions. The term “mountain” is associated with the idea of purity, quality and authenticity.

The mountain area is recognized for its low pollution, which makes the food originating from this area more valuable. This type of food is healthier, because the livestock in the mountain area feeds on a larger variety of plants, some of which are medicinal. The raw materials, as well as the food for the livestock from the mountain area, help maintain the biodiversity and the traditional agricultural practices, ensure safety of the food, they are fresh and highly qualitative, they contribute to the development of the local economy by creating employment and they raise the standard of living.

European legislation regulating the quality scheme “Mountain product”: Reg. (EU) 1151/2012 regarding conditions of use of the optional quality term “mountain product”, reserving the term “mountain product” for food products produced and processed in the mountains; Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 665/2014 of 11 March 2014 supplementing Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to conditions of use of the optional quality term “mountain product”.

National legislation: Government Decision no. 506 of 20 July 2016 with regard to establishing the institutional framework and certain measures to apply the provisions of the Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 665/2014; Order No. 174/2021 with regards to the approval of the Procedure of verification of conformity of the data in the tender for the right to use the quality term “mountain product” and for the control to verify the compliance with European and national legislation by the economic operators that have been granted the right to use the respective quality term..

Keywords: *mountain area, mountain product, European legislation, national legislation.*

INTRODUCTION

In the mountains, the agriculture is confronted by multiple limitations, related to the existence of permanent natural challenges, that are not easy to approach with investments. Low temperatures, a limited period of crop growth, are combined with steep gradients and low fertility soils and it necessitates more complex machinery and longer work time. This results in a lower work and land productivity. Such limitations also result for the agricultors in fewer options of productive sectors they can invest in. The farms are therefore smaller, on average, compared to those in the lower flatlands. Poor access increases difficulties for mountain farms and have effects on the food industry in the mountains (higher collection and transport costs, smaller structures that imply lower economies of scale). The existence of traditions and specific knowledge related to the agricultural production and food processing

in the mountain area is an opportunity for the mountain communities, strengthened by the synergy with the tourism.

In order for the mountain products reaching the market to be identified easier and as such less deceiving for the consumer, the EU institutions have regulated a common definition for an optional quality term, “Mountain Product”, to use on the labels of the products destined for human consumption, products originating from the mountain area.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The aim of this study is to identify all the normative acts that regulate the right to use the quality term “mountain product”. It starts from the first steps taken within the association of the countries with mountains – Euromontana, steps further used by the European Parliament and transformed in community legislation – Regulations (EU). These were the basis for the national legislation: Government Decisions and minister orders.

1. The delineation of the mountain area

According to the delineation established by the Common order of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development no. 97/2019 and the Ministry of Regional Development and Public Administration no. 1332/2019, the Romanian mountain area includes 948 settlements (947 administrative territorial units and one belonging village), totalling 38.31% of the national territory (OM 97/1332, 2019) within 27 counties that comprise mountains (Fig. 1). Their situation is as follows: 30 municipalities, 83 towns, 835 communes.

Fig. 1. The delineation of the mountain area in România

Source: National Mountain Area Agency

In the mountain area there is a total population of 4,891,145 people representing 21.97 % of the population in Romania (Fig. 1).

2. The origin of the concept of “mountain product” quality term

In 2000 has taken place in Trento, Italy, the European convention of the mountain areas in Europe – Euromontana (Ungureanu, 2014) and, with this occasion, an exhibition of agri-food products: The quality mountain products show. The final declaration of the Convention has included the recognition of the specificity and promotion of the food products from the mountain areas.

In the period 2002–2004, Euromontana has made a study financed by DG Recherche (EC) on the products in the mountain area, showing that only 39 products out of the 122 studied from the mountain areas, had an AOP/ IGP certification.

This prompted further local and regional initiatives of various professional associations and of the civil society for the definition of a specific legislation.

Euromontana has launched in 2005 the European Charter for Mountain quality food products and presented it to the European Parliament.

The European Charter for Mountain quality food products was launched under the supervision of Mr. Robert Daul, President of the Committee for Agriculture and Rural Development of the European Parliament and in the presence of Mr. Jacques Barrot, Comissary for Transport and Vice-President of the European Comission.

The Charter was aiming to put in practice the intentions of the parties to protect and promote the quality mountain food products and to contribute to the sustainable development of the territories and economies of the mountain areas in Europe. It was signed by 54 states, regions and organisations from 11 countries (Ungureanu, 2014). Among the parties present at the European Parliament there were: the State Secretary from the Ministry of Local Governance and Regional Development of Norway, the State Secretary from the Ministry of Agriculture from Romania and the representative of the Minister for Agriculture’s cabinet from France. Other prestigious members of the European Parliament, led by Mme Catherine Guy-Quint, Vice-President of AEM, have also signed the Charter, together with representatives of the producers, the Committee of the agricultural professional organisations – the General Committee for agricultural cooperation of the European Union/ The Committee of the agricultural professional organisations – The General Confederation of the agricultural cooperatives COPA & COGECA.

Among the parties from Romania were: The Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, The Training and Innovation Center for Development in the Carpathians – CEFIDEC, The AgromRo Association, The Institute for Research and Development for Mountainology Cristian – Sibiu.

In December 2005 the Charter was launched at the European Parliament.

The five principles of the Charter established the following (Ungureanu, 2014):

- The raw materials have to originate from the mountain area
- The processing must take place in the mountain area
- Production must integrate the local concerns about the sustainable development
- Production must favor preservation of biodiversity and heritage of the mountain areas
- Production must guarantee to the consumers information transparency at any moment.

In the period 2007–2010 Euromontana has worked on Project EuroMARC, based on conclusions from previous studies, as well as on The European Charter for Mountain quality food products. This project was aimed at studying the consumers' interest for the mountain quality agri-food products (MQFP) and the conditions to develop supply chains in the mountain areas.

The objectives of Project EuroMARC targeted:

- Assessment of consumers' interest for agri-food products;
- Analyzing the way supply chains can positively impact the economical situation of a region;
- Identifying difficulties that can arise along the supply chain: production–transformation/processing–retailing the MQFP;
- Collecting as much data as possible to form a clear and correct definition for the “mountain product”.

Project EuroMARC has drawn the following Conclusions and Recommendations:

- The development opportunity for mountain quality agri-food products (MQFP) represents a large potential because of the positive image the mountain products have in consumers' preferences, as a result of their characteristics: natural and specific;
- The existence of a somewhat latent demand for the mountain products, but one that can be increased through the differentiation of a market segment identified as “mountain product”;
- The suggestion that an action plan must be adopted at the EU level for a better valorisation of the mountain quality food products.

Thus, on 21 November 2012 the European Parliament and the European Union Council have adopted a new Regulation: Reg. (UE) 1151/2012, that was published in the Official Journal of the EU (Socio-economic analysis, 2017).

3. European legislation regulating the optional quality term “mountain product”

1. Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 November 2012 on quality schemes for agricultural products and foodstuffs (R EU no. 115, 2012).

Regulation (EU) No. 1151/2012 has established a system applicable to the optional quality terms, to help producers communicate on the domestic market the characteristics or the properties that add value to their agricultural products. This regulates the conditions to use the optional quality term “mountain product” and empowers the Commission to adopt delegate acts to lay down derogations from the conditions of use, in duly justified cases and to take into account the natural restraints that affect the agricultural production in the mountain areas.

Art. 31 of this Regulation refers distinctly to the Mountain product:

(1) The term “mountain product” is established as an optional quality term.

This term shall only be used to describe products intended for human consumption listed in Annex I to the Treaty in respect of which:

(a) both the raw materials and the feedstuffs for farm animals come essentially from mountain areas;

(b) in the case of processed products, the processing also takes place in mountain areas.

2. For the purposes of this Article, mountain areas within the Union are those delimited pursuant to Article 18(1) of Regulation (EC) No 1257/1999. For third-country products, mountain areas include areas officially designated as mountain areas by the third country or that meet criteria equivalent to those set out in Article 18(1) of Regulation (EC) No 1257/1999 (Ungureanu, 2017).

4. National legislation regulating the optional quality term “mountain product”

In 2016 was issued the national regulation framework for the Mountain Product (Ungureanu, 2020):

1. Government Decision no. 506 of 20 July 2016 with regards to the institutional framework and certain measures to apply Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 665/2014 of 11 March 2014 supplementing Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to conditions of use of the optional quality term “mountain product” (R D EU 665, 2014);

2. Order No. 52/2017 with regards to the approval of the Procedure of verification of conformity of the data in the tender for the right to use the quality term “mountain product” and for the control to verify the compliance with European and national legislation by the economic operators that have been granted the right to use the respective quality term.

This normative act has undergone a series of ulterior amendments and completions:

3. Order no. 321 of 28 September 2017 of the minister of agriculture and rural development to amend the annex to the Order no. 52/2017 with regards to the approval of the Procedure of verification of conformity of the data in the tender for the right to use the quality term “mountain product” and for the control to verify the compliance with European and national legislation by the economic operators that have been granted the right to use the aforementioned quality term. – the amendment was necessary following the amendment of the Government Decision no. 912/2017, that designated the Mountain Area Agency as the competent authority.

4. Order no. 31 of 31 January 2018 of the minister of agriculture and rural development for the amendment of the annex to the Order No. 52/2017 with regards to the approval of the Procedure of verification of conformity of the data in the tender for the right to use the quality term “mountain product” and for the control to verify the compliance with European and national legislation by the economic operators that have been granted the right to use the respective quality term – amendment necessary to regulate certain aspects with regards to granting the rights to use the optional quality term ‘mountain product’, because this activity was done jointly by the Mountain Area Agency and the County Agricultural Directorates (CAD) in the mountain area.

5. Order no. 49 of 14 January 2019 for the amendment and completion of the annex to Order No. 52/2017 with regards to the approval of the Procedure of verification of conformity of the data in the tender for the right to use the quality term “mountain product” and for the control to verify the compliance with European and national legislation by the economic operators that have been granted the right to use the respective quality term – amendment for the national logo, exclusive property of the Mountain Area Agency, (OM no. 49, 2019),

logo that will be applied on all products that receive the right to use the optional quality term “mountain product” (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. The “Mountain Product” logo

Source: National Agency for Mountain Area

6. Order no. 328 of 31 May 2019 of the minister of agriculture and rural development for the amendment of the annex to Order No. 52/2017 with regards to the approval of the Procedure of verification of conformity of the data in the tender for the right to use the quality term “mountain product” and for the control to verify the compliance with European and national legislation by the economic operators that have been granted the right to use the respective quality term – the amendment was necessary following the restructuring of the Mountain Area Agency into the National Agency for the Mountain Area and hence the necessity to replace the syntax “Mountain Area Agency” with “National Agency for the Mountain Area”, throughout the entirety of Order no. 52/2017.

7. Order no. 585 of 20 December 2019 for the amendment of the Order No. 52/2017 with regards to the approval of the Procedure of verification of conformity of the data in the tender for the right to use the quality term “mountain product” and for the control to verify the compliance with European and national legislation by the economic operators that have been granted the right to use the respective aforementioned quality term.

Following the restructuring of the Mountain Area Agency into the National Agency for the Mountain Area, Regional Centers for Mountain Development (RCMD) and Offices for Mountain Development (OMD) were created, non-legal entities subordinated to the Agency. During 2019, 80% of the staff for these offices and centers was employed, leading to a necessity to extend the activity of granting the right to use the optional quality term ‘mountain product’ and to verify the compliance with European and national law by the economic operators that have been granted the right to use the quality term by the Agency staff in the territory. Thus, the prerogatives of the CADs were transferred by this order to the staff from the RCMD and OMD.

9. Order No. 174/2021 with regards to the approval of the Procedure of verification of conformity of the data in the tender for the right to use the quality term “mountain product”

and for the control to verify the compliance with European and national legislation by the economic operators (OM no. 174, 2021) that have been granted the right to use the respective quality term.

CONCLUSIONS

Regulation (UE) No. 1151/2012 establishes the need to implement quality systems based on quality terms that bring added value to products, that can be communicated on the domestic market and are applied optionally. Using the quality term adds value compared to similar products.

The quality scheme has been implemented at EU level because:

- The quality and diversity of agri-food production in the mountain area are its strong points, representing a competitive advantage for the producers in the mountain area, significantly contributing to its present cultural and culinary heritage.
- Using quality systems for producers that will reward them for their efforts to produce a wide variety of quality products is beneficial for the rural economy. This is particularly relevant for the less favored areas, in the mountains, where the agricultural sector is an important part of the economy and where production costs are high.
- Producers can keep offering a wide variety of high quality products only if they are properly rewarded for their efforts. This implies the capacity to inform buyers and consumers about the characteristics of their products, in fair competition conditions.
- Citizens and consumers of the EU are asking for quality products more and more frequently, as well as traditional products, while at the same time being concerned by the preservation of the diversity of the agricultural production. This situation generates a demand of agricultural products or foodstuffs with certain identifiable characteristics, particularly concerning their geographical origins.

For the producers, obtaining the right to use the optional quality term “mountain product” is necessary for the following reasons:

- To better valorify the fruits of their work. The quality and diversity of the agri-food production in the mountain area are their strong points, representing a competitive advantage for the producers in the mountain area.
- To succeed in communicating on the market the characteristics and properties that add value to their products. A mountain product is seen by the consumers as a superior quality product with a certified origin, obtained from an area with low pollution.
- To inform consumers and buyers about the properties of their products, in fair competition conditions, in order to preserve the authenticity of the products intended for human consumption, originating from the mountain area and to add value to the products, based on their origin.
- To avoid the abusive use of the term ‘mountain’ and to regulate the fact that the product granted the right to use this quality term has been verified and certified as a product originating from the mountain area.
- To be able to use the logo “Mountain Product” certifying the mountain origin of the raw materials, of the product and of the processing area.
- To protect the local gastronomic heritage of the mountain areas.
- To enable them to access non-refundable financing to promote and market the products certified through quality schemes recognised at European level.

- To benefit from a VAT level reduced to 5% on the sale of their products.
- To be a part of the Association “Mountain Product”, a professional association of the producers that have been granted the right to use the optional quality term “mountain product”.

Selling the products within the mountain farm will be beneficial for the farmer – obtaining complementary incomes – as well as for the consumer, beneficiary of healthy agri-food products.

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